

ON FAILURE MODES IN FINITE WIDTH ANGLE PLY LAMINATES

C. T. HERAKOVICH

Virginia Pol. Inst. and NASA, U.S.A.

Results of a failure analysis of finite width $[\pm\theta]$ T300/5208 graphite-epoxy laminates subjected to thermal curing loads and applied tensile strain are presented. Stress distributions obtained from linear elastic and linear thermo-elastic finite element stress analyses are used in conjunction with the tensor polynomial failure criterion to predict the mode and location of first failure in laminates with fiber angles ranging from five to seventy-five degrees. It is shown that the mode of failure is predominantly interlaminar shear for small fiber angles, shifts to combined interlaminar normal, inplane shear and inplane normal for intermediate angles, and is primarily transverse tension for large fiber angles. The location of initial failure shifts from the $\pm\theta$ interface for small fiber angles to the midplane for large fiber angles.

INTRODUCTION

Numerical results for stress distributions in finite width composite laminates have shown that a complex three-dimensional stress state is present in the boundary layer region along the free edges [1]. Further analysis of the free edge problem is warranted because the stress concentrations in the boundary layer are believed to be the primary cause of the low strength exhibited by some laminates [2-10].

Most previous discussions of edge initiated laminate failure have been based upon the rather simple maximum strain failure criterion [2-4] or a fracture mechanics approach [5,6]. This paper is concerned with the influence of stress interaction on the initiation of failure in laminates which are assumed to be initially free of cracks and voids. The tensor polynomial failure criterion [11] is used to predict the initiation of failure based upon stress distributions obtained from a finite element stress analysis. It is well known that many laminates have the ability to carry additional load after the onset of local damage in the form of microcracking. This paper will not attempt to follow the progression of damage from the initiation stage to ultimate failure. Rather, the emphasis will be placed upon the mode and location of initial failure as a function of fiber orientation. However, it will be shown that fiber orientation has a profound influence on the strength of boundary layer effects, and thus has a direct bearing on progressive versus catastrophic failure.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

Thermo-elastic Stress Analysis

The three-dimensional thermo-elastic constitutive equation for an orthotropic lamina with the fibers oriented at an angle θ with the global x-axis (Fig. 1) can be written in the form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{11} & \bar{C}_{12} & \bar{C}_{13} & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{16} \\ \bar{C}_{12} & \bar{C}_{22} & \bar{C}_{23} & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{26} \\ \bar{C}_{13} & \bar{C}_{23} & \bar{C}_{33} & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{36} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{44} & \bar{C}_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{45} & \bar{C}_{55} & 0 \\ \bar{C}_{16} & \bar{C}_{26} & \bar{C}_{36} & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{66} \end{bmatrix}^k \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x - \epsilon_x^T \\ \epsilon_y - \epsilon_y^T \\ \epsilon_z - \epsilon_z^T \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{zx} \\ \gamma_{xy} - \gamma_{xy}^T \end{Bmatrix}^k \quad (1)$$

where $[\bar{C}]$ is the transformed stiffness matrix

$\{\epsilon\}$ is the total strain vector

$\{\epsilon^T\}$ is the free thermal strain vector

$\{\sigma\}$ is the stress vector

and k refer to the k^{th} layer of the laminate.

As indicated in Eq. (1) there is coupling between shear and normal effects because \bar{C}_{16} , \bar{C}_{26} and \bar{C}_{36} are generally non-zero. There is also coupling between yz and xz shear effects due to the presence of the non-zero \bar{C}_{45} .

FIGURE 1. FINITE WIDTH LAMINATE SUBJECTED TO TENSILE LOAD

Since the laminate is long in the x -direction and the tensile loads are applied at the ends, the states of stress and strain are independent of the axial coordinate. The most general displacement field for this problem can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= \xi x + U(y, z) \\
 v &= V(y, z) \\
 w &= W(y, z)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

where ξ is the applied axial strain. Thus, the problem reduces to the determination of the displacement functions $U(y, z)$, $V(y, z)$, and $W(y, z)$. For the thermal problem ξ is also unknown. Symmetry allows the investigation to be limited to one quarter of the cross section for thin laminates.

Finite Element Stress Analysis

The finite element method of solution was chosen because of its versatility with irregular shape geometries and material inhomogeneity. The region of interest was subdivided into a finite number of triangular elements as shown in Fig. 2. As indicated in the figure, a very dense, uniform mesh was used near the free edge. The results presented in this paper were obtained from two similar, but slightly different meshes. The finer of the two was used for the purely elastic loadings and the other for the thermoelastic loadings. The finer mesh had thirty-two through-the-thickness elements near the free edge and the coarser mesh had sixteen through-the-thickness elements at the free edge. The displacement fields (U, V, W) were represented by linear interpolation functions resulting in constant stress and strain over each element. The unknown nodal displacements U_i , V_i , and W_i (and ξ in the thermal problem) were then determined by standard procedures.

Failure Criterion

The availability of all six components of stress provides a unique opportunity to study stress interaction in a fully three-dimensional failure criterion. The tensor polynomial criterion proposed by Tsai and Wu was chosen for this investigation. This criterion postulates the existence of a failure surface of the form

$$F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j = 1 \quad (3)$$

where F_i and F_{ij} are strength tensors whose components can be expressed in terms of the material principal strengths. When expanded in material principal coordinates for an orthotropic material Eq. (3) has the form

$$\begin{aligned} & F_1 \sigma_1^2 + F_2 \sigma_2^2 + F_3 \sigma_3^2 + F_{11} \sigma_1^4 + F_{22} \sigma_2^4 + F_{33} \sigma_3^4 \\ & + F_{44} \tau_{23}^2 + F_{55} \tau_{13}^2 + F_{66} \tau_{12}^2 + 2F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + 2F_{13} \sigma_1 \sigma_3 + 2F_{23} \sigma_2 \sigma_3 = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

It is also instructive to express the failure criterion in laminate coordinates for analysis of failure at free edges and surfaces where selected components of stress must be zero. The form of the criterion in laminate coordinates is

$$\begin{aligned} & F'_1 \sigma_x^2 + F'_2 \sigma_y^2 + F'_3 \sigma_z^2 + F'_6 \tau_{xy}^2 + F'_{11} \sigma_x^4 + F'_{22} \sigma_y^4 + F'_{33} \sigma_z^4 \\ & + F'_{44} \tau_{yz}^2 + F'_{55} \tau_{xz}^2 + F'_{66} \tau_{xy}^2 + 2F'_{16} \sigma_x \tau_{xy} + 2F'_{26} \sigma_y \tau_{xy} \\ & + 2F'_{36} \sigma_z \tau_{xy} + 2F'_{45} \tau_{yz} \tau_{xz} + 2F'_{12} \sigma_x \sigma_y + 2F'_{13} \sigma_x \sigma_z \\ & + 2F'_{23} \sigma_y \sigma_z = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Evaluation of the individual terms of the polynomials (4) and (5) for each finite element gives an indication of the mode of first failure.

FIGURE 2. FINITE ELEMENT REPRESENTATION OF QUARTER LAMINATE

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Previous numerical results have shown the existence of stress concentrations in a boundary layer along the free edge of laminated composites. The strength of the stress concentration in $[\pm\theta]_S$ laminates varies with fiber orientation as shown in Figs. 3 and 4. These figures^S show the normalized maximum value of each component of stress as a function of fiber orientation for residual curing stresses and for combined thermo-mechanical loading. The thermo-mechanical results correspond to the condition of first failure for tensile loading with residual curing stresses included in the analysis.

As can be seen in Fig. 3 for residual stresses due to curing, five of the six components of stress attain their maximum value at a fiber orientation of 45° . The one exception is the σ_x component of stress which attains its maximum at $\theta=30^\circ$. It is interesting to note^x that although $\sigma_x = \sigma_y$ in the interior of the laminae for $\theta=45^\circ$ (lamination theory), such is not the case in the boundary layer where lamination theory is not valid. These residual thermal stress results lead one to suspect that the $[\pm 45]_S$ laminate is the most susceptible to failure due to thermal loading. The peak stress^S values at 45° are of course the result of the mismatch in thermal properties being maximum for this laminate.

The maximum stress results in Fig. 4 for combined thermo-mechanical loading indicate a θ dependence which is quite different from the thermal loading results. (The results in Fig. 4 correspond to the stresses at first failure under tensile strain.) Only the inplane shear component τ_{xy} exhibits its maximum value at 45° . All other components attain their maximum at smaller angles. Three components, σ_y , σ_z , and τ_{yz} , attain their maximum values at $\theta=30^\circ$, τ_{xz} attains its maximum at $\theta=15^\circ$, and σ_x is maximum for the unidirectional material. Thus, the most critical fiber^x orientation for first failure due to tensile loading is not obvious.

This question is resolved in Fig. 5 which shows the maximum normalized value of the tensor polynomial as a function of fiber orientation for pure tensile loading of angle-ply laminates. The critical angle is seen to be 15° . Examination of the individual terms of the tensor polynomial, Eq. (4), indicated that the failure for this critical fiber angle was dominated by the τ_{13} interlaminar shear term. These results, combined with those in Fig. 4, show that the dominant stress component in the initiation of failure is τ_{xz} , the only component of stress which attains its maximum value at 15° . In view of Eq. (1) this peak shear stress at $\theta=15^\circ$ is the result of high shear strains γ_{yz} and γ_{zx} and the magnitude of the stiffness coefficients \bar{C}_{45} and \bar{C}_{55} . Failure initiated at the $\pm\theta$ interface for fiber angles equal to or less than 30° , but shifted to the laminate midplane for larger angles.

The through-the-thickness dependence of the tensor polynomial with fiber orientation for thermal curing and thermal plus mechanical loading is shown in Fig. 6. The results were determined for the finite elements along the free edge. The thermal loading results verify the previously conjectured conclusion that the $[\pm 45]_S$ laminate is the most sensitive to thermal loading. The figure shows large through-the-thickness gradients centered about the $\pm\theta$ interface for $\theta=45^\circ$. Both the magnitude of the polynomial and the gradients decrease in magnitude as the angle varies from 45° .

The combined thermal plus mechanical loading results at first failure in Fig. 6 exhibit a fiber direction dependence which is quite different from the pure fiber angles and generally decrease with increasing angle. The largest gradient is at $\theta=15^\circ$, the critical angle for mechanical loading. The combination of thermal plus mechanical loading is shown to produce an interesting effect for $\theta=45^\circ$. The high thermal stresses near the interface combine with the stresses due to mechanical loading to produce a negative gradient centered about the interface. In contrast

a) Intralaminar Stresses

b) Interlaminar Stresses

FIGURE 3. NORMALIZED MAXIMUM CURING STRESSES IN $[\pm\theta]_s$ LAMINATES

a) Intralaminar Stresses

b) Interlaminar Stresses

FIGURE 4. NORMALIZED MAXIMUM STRESSES AT FIRST FAILURE IN $[\pm\theta]_s$ LAMINATES UNDER TENSILE STRAIN WITH CURING STRESSES

FIGURE 5. NORMALIZED MAXIMUM TENSOR POLYNOMIAL VALUES FOR $[\pm\theta]_s$ LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO TENSILE STRAIN

to the results for all other angles, the tensor polynomial exhibits its smallest value at the $\pm\theta$ interface for $\theta=45^\circ$. First failure under combined thermo-mechanical loading was predicted to occur at the interface for all laminates except the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate which was predicted to fail at the midplane. (Due to numerical roundoff,^s elements adjacent to the interface sometimes failed before elements at the interface. This explains why the maximum values shown in Fig. 6 are not always equal to one.)

The state of stress on the element that was predicted to exhibit first failure under thermo-mechanical loading was transformed to material principal coordinates for each fiber orientation and the individual terms of the tensor polynomial (Eq. 4) were evaluated. The results are shown in Table 1. For fiber angles of 10° and 15° , the polynomial is clearly dominated by shear with the interlaminar shear stress τ_{13} being the dominate stress. Thus the mode of failure is interlaminar shear. At $\theta=30^\circ$, first failure is still dominated by shear effects, but all three shear components make significant contributions to the tensor polynomial for this fiber angle. Failure is a mixed shear mode. The sensitivity of fiber angle is demonstrated by a comparison of the results for 30° and 45° . While the interlaminar shear stresses contributed 87 percent of the polynomial at 30° , their contribution is zero at 45° . Failure at 45° is mixed σ_2 - τ_{12} with σ_2 being the dominate stress. For $\theta=60^\circ$ and 75° , failure is dominated by σ_2 , i.e. transverse tension.

The influence of boundary layer effects on the initiation of failure is clearly demonstrated in Fig. 7. This figure shows the distribution of the tensor polynomial, at first failure, along the $\pm\theta$ interface for fiber angles ranging from 10° to 75° . The loading is combined residual thermal plus applied tensile strain. The boundary layer effect is very strong at small fiber angles and decreases as the angle increases. For angles of 10° and 15° , the polynomial is actually negative away from the edge, but exhibits a very sharp gradient in the boundary layer rising to

FIGURE 6. THROUGH-THE-THICKNESS TENSOR POLYNOMIAL DISTRIBUTIONS FOR CURING STRESSES AND STRESSES AT FIRST FAILURE IN $[\pm\theta]_S$ LAMINATES

a value equal to or greater than 1.0 at the free edge. (An incremental loading procedure was used for the thermo-mechanical problem and no attempt was made to interpolate between increments to determine the exact failure strain.) The maximum value of the polynomial always occurred at the free edge. For large fiber angles, the boundary layer effects are much less pronounced with the interior region exhibiting values approaching 1.0 as the angle increases. These results confirmed the argument of Pipes et al [2] that there are two modes of failure for finite-width angle-ply laminates. A laminate mode based upon lamination theory is adequate for large fiber angles, but a free-edge mode, dominated by interlaminar effects in the boundary layer, is required for small fiber angles. The results in this paper indicate that the mode of failure changes from free-edge to laminate between fiber angles of thirty and forty-five degrees. However, as indicated in Fig. 7, failure initiates at the free edge for all fiber angles.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The tensor polynomial failure criterion has been used in conjunction with finite element stress results for the stress-distributions in finite width angle-ply composite laminates subjected to thermo-mechanical loading. It has been shown that edge effects dominate the initiation of failure for small fiber angles, but that they are not as severe for large fiber angles. Additional work is required in order to experimentally verify the predictions presented here and to more fully understand the cumulative damage process from the initiation of microcracking to ultimate failure.

FIGURE 7. TENSOR POLYNOMIAL DISTRIBUTIONS ALONG THE INTERFACE OF $[\pm\theta]_S$ LAMINATES FOR FIRST FAILURE UNDER TENSILE STRAIN WITH CURING STRESSES

Laminate	$F_1\sigma_1$	$F_{11}\sigma_1^2$	$F_2\sigma_2$	$F_{22}\sigma_2^2$	$F_3\sigma_3$	$F_{33}\sigma_3^2$	$F_{44}\tau_{23}^2$	$F_{55}\tau_{13}^2$	$F_{66}\tau_{12}^2$
$[\pm 10]_s$.0273	.0576	-.0715	.0025	.0079	.0000	.0494	.9016	.0216
$[\pm 15]_s$.0231	.0409	-.1043	-.0054	-.0101	.0001	.1145	.8808	.0443
$[\pm 30]_s$.0163	.0204	-.1241	.0076	-.0729	.0026	.3305	.5382	.2750
$[\pm 45]_s$.0027	.0005	.6070	.1823	.0315	.0005	.0000	.0000	.1793
$[\pm 60]_s$	-.0003	.0000	.6770	.2266	.0302	.0005	.0311	.0048	.0300
$[\pm 75]_s$	-.0002	.0000	.7135	.2517	.0115	.0001	.0179	.0006	.0048

TABLE 1. INDIVIDUAL TERMS OF THE TENSOR POLYNOMIAL AT FAILURE

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